

Evaluation of Educational Productivity in Secondary Schools in Zone 10 of Villahermosa using the TIEP Model

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Resumen

La productividad en las instituciones educativas es un factor determinante para mejorar la calidad y equidad escolar. En este estudio se aplicó la Técnica Integral de Evaluación de la Productividad (TIEP), complementada con el análisis PESTEL, a una secundaria pública de la zona escolar 10 de Villahermosa, Tabasco. Los hallazgos muestran fortalezas en la planeación estratégica y la gestión directiva, pero también debilidades en innovación, interacción social y comprensión de procesos internos. Los resultados evidencian que la productividad educativa no solo depende de los recursos académicos, sino también del entorno socioeconómico y cultural particular de Tabasco. Se concluye que el TIEP es una herramienta estratégica para diagnosticar y proponer acciones de mejora específicas al contexto local, contribuyendo a la consolidación de una educación inclusiva y de calidad en la región.

Abstract

Productivity in educational institutions is a determining factor in improving educational quality and equity. This study applied the Comprehensive Productivity Evaluation Technique (CPE), complemented by PESTEL analysis, to a public secondary school in school zone 10 of Villahermosa, Tabasco. The findings reveal strengths in strategic planning and management, but also weaknesses in innovation, social interaction, and understanding of internal processes. The results demonstrate that educational productivity depends not only on academic resources but also on the specific socioeconomic and cultural environment of Tabasco. It is concluded that CPE is a strategic tool for diagnosing and proposing improvement actions specific to the local context, contributing to the consolidation of inclusive, quality education in the region.

Palabras Clave: Productividad educativa, TIEP, escuelas secundarias, PESTEL

Keywords: Educational productivity, TIEP, secondary schools, PESTEL

1. INTRODUCTION

A country's economic capacity is reflected by its growth in education. "Broadly speaking, the more educated a country's population is, the greater its opportunities to progress in terms of employability and technological innovation, which boosts the growth and development of society" (MEXICO, 2023).

The importance that some countries have given to education has not been particularly successful in terms of results, even with the efforts of authorities to address educational issues with the goal of changing and improving the structure of each educational system through educational reforms and a new educational model.

Productivity in Mexico's public educational institutions is a key element in ensuring high-quality education, reducing inequalities between regions, and, above all, driving national economic progress. When school management is carried out effectively, material, human, and financial resources can be maximized, resulting in a more favorable learning environment and, therefore, better academic outcomes. According to the Bank of Mexico (2020), if the southern regions of the country achieved educational standards similar to those of the

north, the country's total productivity could increase by up to 13% (An Education and Productivity Model for the Regions of Mexico 1, n.d.).

Furthermore, greater effectiveness in education helps develop human capital with more robust skills for entering the workforce, which positively impacts the nation's competitiveness (INEE, 2019). The implementation of results-focused tactics, the appropriate use of educational technologies, and ongoing teacher training are essential aspects for improving the effectiveness of the public education system. Along these lines, productivity should be viewed not only as an administrative issue, but as a fundamental element in ensuring the right to a fair and quality education.

In the education sector, it is seen as essential to implement productivity evaluation methods comparable to those used by companies, which use these indicators as competitiveness indices. From this perspective, educational institutions should apply evaluation methods based on holistic approaches that enable a systematic assessment of performance. In line with the proposals of Eliseo-Dantés et al. (2024), productivity evaluation should include systems that allow for a fair and equitable evaluation of staff performance, considering both individual and collective effort, with the aim of allocating incentives based on the benefits generated.

Productivity in education

“Productivity in education allows for better results with the least effort. Thus, we have, on the one hand, production, quantity, quality, performance, investment, goods and services, and on the other, the training of human resources and the acquisition of skills” (Rodríguez, n.d.).

Rodríguez, n.d., mentions that productivity is presented as a combination of quantitative and qualitative indices that allow us to assess and analyze the progress, development, and advancement of any educational process. To this end, we propose a measurement technique created by Eliseo Dantés, 2024. The technique is called TIEP (Comprehensive Productivity Evaluation Technique). For this technique, it is important to apply a strategic tool such as PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Ecological, and Legal) to analyze the external variables of the context where the research is carried out. The results obtained will allow us to specify the weight to be given to each element when applying the TIEP instrument.

Debemos de tener presente que para que se puedan dar los resultados de una manera viables y objetiva debe de existir una cultura prepositiva en la medición de la productividad como lo menciona Eliseo Dantes, 2024 y que los conocimientos plenos a nivel productividad integral de las empresas e instituciones es el de mantener todas las áreas funcionales con involucramiento de todo el personal, donde se integren y equilibren diversas variables con el fin de determinar índices que influyan directamente en la eficacia operativa y administrativa de la institución.

For this study, the sector where the proposed measurement instrument is applied is defined for elementary school students in secondary schools in the central municipality of Villahermosa.

Álvarez Méndez (2019) mentions that the application of a measurement instrument is essential for improving various aspects of the educational environment, such as academic performance and the objective evaluation of teaching staff performance. Furthermore, the author highlights that this practice allows for the

identification of strengths and weaknesses within the educational process, which significantly contributes to its continuous improvement.

Productivity in the educational context

Educational efficiency is a crucial issue in Mexican government policies, especially in the face of current economic and demographic challenges. According to the Center for Economic and Budgetary Research (CIEPE), demographic change in Mexico will lead to a decline in the working-age population and an increase in the aging population. In this context, it is essential that the education system, renewed through the New Mexican School, foster increased human productivity so that future generations are able to adapt to the country's new demographic conditions (CIEP, Alberto, 2022).

Measuring Productivity in Schools

Evaluating productivity in secondary schools involves assessing indicators such as completion rate, dropout rate, and academic performance. The National Commission for the Continuous Improvement of Education (MEJOREDU) has established national metrics that facilitate monitoring ongoing progress in education in Mexico. For example, from 2017 to 2021, dropout rates (dropouts) showed a notable reduction in secondary education, where the dropout rate fell by 1.7 percentage points, according to (MEJOREDU, 2022).

Context of secondary schools in Tabasco

In Tabasco, the Ministry of Education has implemented guidelines and tactics to enhance the quality of education and the effectiveness of educational centers. The purpose of the 2020-2024 Sectorial Education Program is to ensure the right to high-quality education, including equity and inclusion. This program complies with current regulations and various legal systems, such as jurisprudence and legislation, including the General Education Law and the General Law of the System for the Career of Teachers (SEP, 2022).

Furthermore, the 2025 National Strategy for Continuing Education in Basic Education seeks to promote the education of basic education teachers and guide national policy regarding continuing education. This strategy is based on the values of the New Mexican School and aims to foster the professional and personal growth of teachers (SEP, 2022).

2. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in a public secondary school in school zone 10 of Villahermosa, Tabasco. A mixed approach was used:

- Quantitative, through the application of the TIEP to various institutional leaders.
- Qualitative, through semi-structured interviews with principals and academic coordinators.

The sample consisted of five senior managers and administrators, including coordinators of academic activities, educational assistance, technology, and comptrollership. The TIEP was adapted to the educational context, encompassing ten key elements: planning, processes, social environment, management participation,

innovation, student knowledge, technological development, macroeconomic understanding, and human resource development.

The analysis was reinforced with the PESTEL tool, which allowed for consideration of the political, social, economic, and cultural factors specific to Tabasco.

Figure 1. Stage of the appealed methodology
Source: Author's elaboration 2025

Research design

The research design is mixed, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques to achieve a more comprehensive view. The implementation of the TIEP model, appropriate for the school environment, demonstrates the quantitative component; the qualitative component, on the other hand, enables the interpretation of participants' perceptions of education (Hernández-Sampieri, Fernández-Collado, & Baptista, 2014). The objective is correlational and descriptive, as it seeks to characterize current productivity circumstances and examine the relationships between internal and external contextual variables (Bisquerra, 2009). Regarding the design, the research is non-experimental and cross-sectional, as data were collected at a single point in time and without manipulation of independent variables (Flick, 2015). It is also classified as an applied study, as it seeks to generate practical proposals for educational improvement (UNESCO, 2017).

Delimitation of the study area

The scope of the study was a public secondary school located in Zone 10 of central Villahermosa, Tabasco. The criteria for delimitation included scheduled appointments, interviewee availability, and those responsible for each process or area, which allowed the analysis to be limited to a specific and representative setting (Yin, 2018).

Unit of analysis and institutional linkage

The unit of analysis was defined as the secondary school, conceived as an educational organization composed of students, teachers, administrators, and parents. To ensure methodological viability, agreements were established with school authorities that facilitated collaboration and guaranteed the transparency of the process through the studies (Bisquerra, 2009).

Adaptation of the TIEP instrument to the educational context

The TIEP instrument was originally designed for work environments in business organizations. Adjustments and modifications were required to adapt the instrument to the educational setting. To conduct the study of productivity in the educational context, the complete instrument was applied. The tool is organized into ten essential elements that cover the functioning of an organization, from strategic planning, human resource management, satisfaction, and internal and external needs. Conducting the study with the instrument provides us with an approach with the main authors within the same context for the acquisition of the required information, leading the institution to recognize and reflect on the opportunities for improvement.

Through a comprehensive approach, the instrument establishes the essential elements for the different aspects of the different variables. Table 1 presents the 10 elements of the TIEP as well as some elements modified and adapted to the educational system.

Table 1. TIEP adapted to the educational context

TIEP	TIEP adapted to the educational context
1 Conceptual approach to the company	Conceptual approach of the educational institution
2 Knowledge of the processes	Knowledge of the processes
3 Social scope of the organization	Community context
4 Planning Management	Educational planning management
5 Management participation	Management participation
6 Creativity and organizational innovation	Creativity and organizational innovation
7 Knowledge of the client(s)	Knowledge of students and families
8 Technological development	Technological development
9 Macroeconomic knowledge	Macroeconomic knowledge
10 Comprehensive development of human resources	Comprehensive development of human resources

The instrument was developed from an evaluation perspective, which means it can be used by the institution's own members for self-assessment, without the need for an external evaluator. This perspective aims to promote an institutional culture based on self-reflection, constant improvement, and decision-making based on the information obtained.

Furthermore, the TIEP instrument is supported by the PESTEL technique, enabling an analysis of the environment in which the educational institution operates. This tool takes into account six essential dimensions: Political, Economic, Environmental, Cultural, Technological, and Social, allowing an evaluation of the aforementioned variables and determining which ones directly or indirectly impact the institution itself. By

including the PESTEL study, the TIEP instrument is enhanced by measuring the institution's productivity not only internally but also externally. The PESTEL analysis evaluates important factors such as political, economic, social, technological, ecological and cultural variables that could influence the institution itself.

- **National and State Education Policies:** Education in Tabasco is governed by the Education Law of the State of Tabasco, which establishes compulsory and free basic education, as well as the secular nature of education.
- **Teacher Training Programs:** The state implements continuing education strategies for teachers, such as the State Strategy for Continuing Education 2023, which seeks to improve educational quality through ongoing training of teaching staff.

Economic

- **Educational Financing:** Financing public education in Tabasco is a shared responsibility among the federal, state, and municipal governments, guaranteeing resources for the proper functioning of educational services.
- **School Infrastructure:** A significant percentage of schools in the municipality of Centro are located in communities outside the city of Villahermosa, which can entail economic challenges related to the maintenance and equipment of these social institutions.
- **Student Diversity:** Tabasco has a diverse population in social, cultural, and economic terms, which represents a challenge for ensuring access to and retention in compulsory education for all students.
- **Multi-grade Schools:** Many public schools in Tabasco are multi-grade, especially in preschool and elementary school, which means that one teacher serves several grades in the same classroom.
- **Technological**
- **Integration of Technologies in Education:** It is essential that public schools incorporate information and communication technologies (ICTs) into their educational processes.
- **Technological Training for Teachers:** Continuing education must include digital skills for the effective use of technological tools in the classroom.

Environmental

- **Geographic Location and Environment:** Tabasco is prone to natural phenomena such as flooding, which can affect school infrastructure and the continuity of classes.
- **Environmental Education:** The education law promotes actions to protect natural resources and the cultural environment.
- **Traditional gender roles:** Stereotypes persist that can limit equity in education.
- **Cultural inequality:** Limited access to artistic and cultural activities.
- **Religion:** Influences school attendance and participation.
- **Proposals:** Contextualized curriculum, intercultural education, inclusive cultural activities, school-community ties, equality campaigns.

Data collection techniques and instruments

The following techniques and instruments were used to collect data:

- Structured questionnaires were administered to the heads of each area and senior management to gather information.
- Semi-structured interviews were conducted with senior management to gain in-depth information about the institution (Flick, 2015).

The instrument was used through interviews using a questionnaire, which made it possible to obtain information for quantification. The interview began by raising awareness among participants, detailing the importance of the exercise in implementing the instrument and explaining the conditions regarding anonymity and privacy of information.

Based on the interviews, the instrument was administered to various members of the educational community, such as the Academic Activities Coordinator, the Technology Activities Coordinator, the Comptroller's Office, the Educational Assistance Coordinator, and the Administrative Services Department. This facilitated a more comprehensive perspective of the institution's productivity.

- Revisión de la información, es el proceso estructurado que brinda la posibilidad de examinar, transformar y organizar datos obtenidos valiosos que facilitaron la toma de decisiones. Este procedimiento transforma datos en bruto en información valiosa, facilitando la comprensión de circunstancias complejas, el descubrimiento de patrones y la creación de vínculos significativos. (Ortega, 2023).

Analysis of results

Descriptive and correlational statistical techniques were used to process the quantitative data, enabling the identification of relevant trends and connections. The qualitative data, meanwhile, were classified and coded to identify common patterns in the participants' discourse, thus strengthening the interpretation of the findings (Yin, 2018).

The information obtained was organized and examined using quantitative and qualitative methods. Numerical data enabled analysis by domain, while open-ended observations provided useful elements to contextualize the results.

It is important to mention that the instrument, in addition to being used as a form of assessment, is also considered a formative and strategic resource. Its objective is to guide the institution and organization in developing proposals based on a diagnosis, fostering a culture of measurement in the commitment to achieving efficiency, effectiveness, and quality in educational services.

The assessment identified the institution's strengths and weaknesses, the direction of human talent growth, and identified areas of opportunity for innovation, its relationship with the environment, and the use of technology, among other factors.

The results are presented in a corresponding report studying the ten elements of the TIEP. This allows for a comprehensive diagnosis of the organization that covers both internal and external factors that could impact The productivity of the secondary education institution. The elements are evaluated from two perspectives:

- The simple average, which represents the direct perception of institutional stakeholders regarding each component.
- The weighted average, which reflects the relative weight or impact that each element has within the organizational whole.

3. RESULTS

Figure 2 presents an analysis for each of the ten elements evaluated, based on the composite average obtained in different areas. Graphical representation facilitates a visualization of each variable specifically for each area; this approach allows for the precise identification of institutional strengths and areas for improvement.

Figure 2. Composite average
Source: Author's elaboration 2025

1. Conceptual Approach of the Educational Institution

With an average score of 1.474, this element reflects that the different areas of the institution have a clear vision of the institutional purposes and objectives. This conceptual alignment contributes to maintaining coherence in school management.

2. Knowledge of Processes

This aspect has a low score (1.304), which suggests deficiencies in the understanding and monitoring of operational processes. Improving this knowledge would strengthen the organization's internal efficiency.

3. Social Sphere of the Organization

This element received the lowest score, with an average of 1.272. This reflects limited interaction with the community environment and limits the possibilities for collaboration with external stakeholders such as the community.

4. Planning Management

This was the highest-rated element (1.55). It indicates that the institution has a solid structure for organizing its activities, setting goals, and coordinating resources.

5. Management Participation

With an average of 1.53, it reflects that school authorities actively participate in institutional processes, which favors effective decision-making.

6. Organizational Creativity and Innovation

Receives one of the lowest scores (1.30). This indicates that traditional practices still prevail and there is resistance or limitations to generating new ideas that improve school dynamics.

7. Knowledge of Students and Families

With a mean of 1.41, this result suggests acceptable knowledge of the student context, although there is still room to strengthen empathy, needs assessment, and family ties.

8. Technological Development

With 1.356 points, it shows intermediate development with little progress, but there are still challenges to fully integrate technology as a pedagogical and administrative tool.

9. Macroeconomic Knowledge

It obtained a mean of 1.46, indicating a relatively good understanding of the economic environment and its implications for school management.

10. Comprehensive human resource development

It achieved an outstanding score of 1.53, demonstrating that the institution has focused on promoting the training and well-being of its staff as a key element of institutional performance.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study demonstrates that educational productivity in Villahermosa's school zone 10 depends both on management and external factors linked to the social and technological context of Tabasco. While strengths are observed in planning and leadership, significant challenges persist in innovation, social interaction, and understanding of internal processes.

The TIEP model, complemented by the PESTEL analysis, is confirmed as an adaptable and effective tool for identifying specific problems in public secondary schools. Its application in Tabasco allows for the generation of contextualized proposals, such as:

1. Greater engagement with the local community to strengthen social participation in education.
2. Promoting pedagogical and technological innovation through teacher training programs and the provision of digital infrastructure.
3. Extending the TIEP model to other schools in Tabasco to construct comparative diagnoses and design more effective state educational strategies.

In short, this work provides a clear diagnosis of school productivity in a specific regional context, offering a replicable model for other basic education institutions in southeastern Mexico.

Recommendations

- Institutional commitment: Encourage management teams to adopt the model as a priority strategic objective, incentivizing the entire educational community to achieve common improvement goals.
- Ongoing training and monitoring: Develop training programs in collaborative work, leadership, and pedagogical innovation, along with technical support to enhance the internal skills of administrative and teaching staff.
- Constant monitoring: Implement continuous assessment systems that make it possible to quantify progress, rectify deviations in a timely manner, and strengthen good practices that can be replicated in other educational settings.

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